

Who Pays for the Commons? Business Model and Financing for Mobility as a Commons Schemes

Amalia Polydoropoulou^{1*}, Athena Tsirimpa², Ioanna Moscholidou¹, Antonis Richetta³,
Ioannis Lymaxis³, Ioanna Fergadiotou³

1. Department of Shipping, Trade and Transport, University of Aegean, Greece

2. The American College of Greece

3. Inlecom Innovation

*polydor@aegean.gr

Abstract

This paper explores the introduction of a new shared mobility solution entitled “Mobility as a Commons” (MaaC). MaaC refers to a concept where mobility services are collectively managed, accessed, and used by a community rather than controlled entirely by private actors or by the state. MaaC as an innovative transport solution is successfully implemented within the Netherlands Mobility Living Lab of the EU-funded GEMINI project where residents are encouraged to move away from individual car ownership to sharing their vehicles with each other, achieving a less car-centered urban mobility system and promoting mobility justice. We present a SWOT analysis of MaaC concept and propose a business model based on the Osterwalder canvas. The business model specifically focuses on the provision of a shared, collectively governed mobility solution alternative to private car ownership and sharing of physical assets and information, emphasising the communities and users sovereignty, sustainability and environmental dimensions of MaaC. We also explore potential financing strategies for the sustainable implementation of MaaC and make recommendations on how to maximise value for all the players involved.

Keywords: *Mobility as a Commons (MaaC), Business Model Canvas, SWOT, Financial Analysis*

1. Introduction

Contemporary research on sustainable mobility highlights the inability of pure technocentric and market driven approaches to produce effective and efficient user-centric solutions to urban transport challenges (Müller-Eie and Kosmidis, 2023). Instead, mobility relates to social, political, and cultural practices included within broad structures of power and inequality (Nikolaeva et al., 2018; Sheller, 2020). The notion of mobility justice supports the inclusion of procedural, restorative, and epistemic justice in addition to distributive fairness. At the core of this re-evaluation of mobility is the concept of Mobility as a Commons (MaaC). MaaC involves a transition from mobility as a commodity to a collective and participatory process. This view stems from the theory of commons and supports that mobility systems should be designed and controlled by their users, with a focus on equality, sustainability, and the community’s needs (Nikolaeva et al., 2019; Beemer et al., 2024). The concept of Mobility as a Common (MaaC) (van Lieverloo and Masttrigt, 2025) represents a significant step forward in the evolution of collective transport solutions, emerging from the foundational practices of carpooling (Shaheen and Cohen, 2013) and the subsequent proliferation of sharing services (Shaheen et al., 2017; Shaheen, 2018). These earlier versions laid the groundwork for MaaC by promoting access over ownership and enhancing the efficiency of transportation networks. Carpooling, one of the earliest forms of shared mobility, operates on the principle of maximizing vehicle occupancy by allowing individuals to share rides, often informally coordinated or facilitated through dedicated platforms. It introduced the notion

that transport resources could be pooled, reducing the environmental burden of individual car use and increasing accessibility for those without private vehicles (Sopjani et al., 2020; Graham-Rowe et al., 2011; Delhomme et al., 2021). The subsequent emergence of digital platforms has further advanced the broader shared mobility ecosystem, facilitating structured sharing services such as car-sharing, bike-sharing, and electric scooter schemes (Narayanan and Antoniou, 2023; Koppelman and Bhat, 2024). These digitally enabled models have significantly contributed to the growth and conceptual development of Mobility as a Service (MaaS), enabling on-demand, flexible transport without ownership (Hensher et al., 2020; Polydoropoulou et al., 2020; Matyas and Kamargianni, 2021; Pagoni et al., 2021; Dadashzadeh et al., 2022; Ho and Tirachini, 2024; Núñez and Antoniou, 2025).

While carpooling and sharing services contribute to improving transport flexibility and reducing car dependency in urban contexts, they often remain embedded in private, profit-oriented models or tend to offer a “one-size-fits-all” solution, limiting fleet choices and mobility flexibility. This commercialization brought with it three main challenges: 1) Platform capitalism (Srnicsek, 2016) has centralized control in the hands of a few tech companies, limiting user agency and transparency; 2. Access to these services tends to be spatially and socioeconomically unequal, concentrated in affluent or central urban neighbourhoods where profitability is highest, thereby excluding lower-income and peri-urban populations (Schor, 2020); and 3. Despite the environmental rhetoric, sustainability remains a secondary concern for many operators, whose growth incentives may conflict with public policy objectives (Nikitas et al., 2020; Moscholidou et al., 2023).

In contrast, MaaC reimagines shared mobility through the lens of commons theory, advocating for a community-governed and inclusively designed mobility ecosystem. Drawing from the work of Ostrom (1990), MaaC emphasizes decentralized governance, collective stewardship, and equitable access to shared transport resources. Unlike traditional sharing models, MaaC platforms are often open-source, cooperative, or municipally managed, with users acting not merely as consumers but as co-creators and decision-makers. This approach ensures that service provision aligns with social goals such as inclusivity, environmental protection and resilience. In addition, it is often the objective of MaaC communities to become self-governed and self-sustaining, and to shape their network and resources in any way they choose.

Sharing mobility resources is not a new concept, but digital platform-based forms of sharing have become popular only in recent decades (Vega-Gonzalo et al., 2024; Schmaus et al., 2025). Platforms such as Uber, Lyft, or Bolt emerged initially with the aim of enabling individuals to utilize their private vehicles as mobility services, allowing asset owners to profit from underused resources. Similarly, non-mobility platforms like Airbnb expanded the concept into other asset-sharing domains, facilitating the rental of properties through digital marketplaces (Chase, 2015). Just over a decade after their boom, many of these platforms have taken a fully commercial character, while their externalities have also been well-documented. For example, Uber’s impact on congestion (Flores and Rayle, 2017) or Airbnb’s impact on housing prices (Franco and Santos, 2021) have been debated and examined extensively. MaaC appears to be a “shift to the basics”, which aims to combine the benefits of digital technology to deliver better use of resources by putting the community in its centre and prioritising self-governance over corporate approaches (Burger and Dormer, 2018).

This paper contributes to the emerging literature on Mobility as a Commons (MaaC) by examining practical insights derived from real-life applications within the GEMINI Living Lab in Amsterdam (Gemini, 2024). Drawing on stakeholder insights and a SWOT analysis, we propose a novel business model for MaaC schemes, highlighting essential parameters including community governance, financial sustainability, and the service’s broader environmental and social impacts.

The following sections are organised as follows: Section 2 presents the concept of MaaC and its genesis in the Netherlands; Section 3 presents insights from local stakeholders; Section 4 identifies the key

enablers and key challenges for establishing MaaC, along with a SWOT analysis for MaaC; Section 5 develops a Business Model of MaaC; Section 6 presents the investment and operation cost of MaaC; and Section 7 concludes the paper highlighting major findings and directions for further research.

2. The MaaC concept

The concept of Mobility as a Commons (MaaC) builds on the idea that mobility resources can be collectively governed and equitably shared within communities. MaaC encourages citizens to move away from private car ownership by sharing vehicles among themselves, providing an inclusive and sustainable alternative in areas where commercial transportation services is unavailable or does not adequately meet local needs. Figure 1 provides a schematic representation of the concept of MaaC, which we divide into three components: the community, community fleet, shared resources and digital enablers such as the MaaC app. More specifically:

The formation of a **community** is at the center of MaaC. It both benefits from (system users) and shapes the shared mobility system (system suppliers).

- The **fleet** comprises different types of vehicles, depending on what is on offer by its members but also reflects the community's needs. For example, unlike corporate bikesharing schemes that offers one-size-fits-all bikes, a MaaC scheme may have a variety of bikes that fit the need of women, children, on or off road conditions as well as cargo bikes, as the different people who share them with the community will have made a variety of choices when buying their bikes. While vehicles are generally privately owned, there are examples of MaaC schemes that gained an official status and have purchased vehicles that are under the shared ownership of the cooperative.
- MaaC is facilitated through a mobile **application**. The application can have many layers, which again can be tailored to meet the needs of the community. The basic features of the application include a booking function, a feature that allows locking/unlocking the vehicle, and geolocation and payment. In addition, the app includes a communication layer, which allows the users to receive information about the vehicle (e.g. notifications for charging or scheduled repairs), which allows for the seamless use of vehicles. The user-friendly app can foster social connections within neighbourhoods promoting community based discussions and collective decision-making. To further support the management of the shared fleet by the members of the community, the MaaC app uses Artificial Intelligence (AI) and can integrate additional tools such as route planning, multimodal transport options, real-time updates, and advanced payment features.
- Finally, MaaC concept is also linked to a range of **shared resources**, which varies between different commons. For example, the community can use private spaces but, where it is possible, it can apply to the city authorities for parking permits, as well as a dedicated parking spaces. Furthermore, the community can also share charging infrastructure for electric vehicles, repair and maintenance tools and skills as well as assets that extend beyond mobility, such as communal spaces.

Figure 1: The concept of MaaC

2.1 MaaC at the Amsterdam Mobility Living Lab (MLL)

In the context of GEMINI’s Horizon Europe research project a Mobility Living Lab (MLL) was established in Amsterdam focusing on the implementation of MaaC and the promotion of shared access to transportation resources (more details on the scheme can be found on: <https://www.geminiproject.eu/discovering-geminis-mobility-living-lab-amsterdam-mobility-as-a-commons-maac/>). The MLL seeks to empower citizens to define their mobility needs and, in collaboration with experts and responsible parties, identify how they can meet these needs through the shared use of their assets. To do so, the scheme is addressed to existing communities that have established cooperative relationships and behaviours, including the sharing of other types of assets, such as common spaces or tools and household items.

The MLL was established by four key consortium partners: the *City of Amsterdam*, coordinates the MLL and is responsible for setting up, running, supervising, monitoring, and evaluating the different communities established; *Townmaking*, working together with the citizens in implementing the MaaC and designing the MaaC administration procedures; *Goodmoovs*, providing the digital infrastructure and supporting the development of a white label MaaC app; and *Cenex*, is knowledge institution supporting the data driven assessment of MaaC, in collaboration with the MLL partners. This collaboration between partners ensures that a multidisciplinary approach and skills shape the MLL, contributing to its inclusiveness and success. In the case of the Amsterdam MLL, the MaaC has been supported by the municipality by designed a new parking permit, known as the cooperative car-sharing permit. Thus, the city provides designated parking spots for the MaaC initiatives, at a location of their own choosing. In addition, the City of Amsterdam has developed scheme was promoted through a variety of channels and a coordinated communication campaign. In more detail, the City of Amsterdam has developed website: www.amsterdam.nl/autodeelgroep that acts as a central hub of information. The website consists of an

explainer video, the conditions to join the pilot and other relevant information. It's also possible to register for the pilot through the website.

The first step to establishing a new MaaC scheme is to establish the Commons itself, which is essentially the community of people in a neighborhood that will share cars. To do so, it is essential to understand the nature of the local context, including its demographic and socioeconomic characteristics, the mobility patterns of different individuals and households living in the area, as well as the unique characteristics of the local built environment and the mix of land uses. In the case of the Amsterdam MLL, this understanding was built through interviews with local people (i.e. narrative record methodology), which helped create a mosaic of local needs and characteristics and understand how these can be best met. Townmaking supported this process through methodological materials, digital infrastructure to capture all of the neighborhood-scale needs, and the necessary knowledge to support those needs across the full lifecycle of the local cooperative. In addition, it should be noted that MaaC communities operate as cooperatives, not aiming to make a profit from shared mobility services and resources. Their goal is to break even each year by adjusting fees to cover actual costs. Support and guidance in developing these cost-sharing models are provided by Townmaking.

Establishing the Commons is the most critical step of establishing the MaaC as it shapes all subsequent choices on the composition of the fleet, the usage arrangements, the pricing, and the flexibility the scheme needs to offer to its users. It also ensures that the scheme aligns with the community's culture, supports its cohesion and enhances its resilience through improved mobility choices. The aforementioned approach empowered citizens and gave them a clear sense of ownership of the scheme, which is considered essential for its long-term viability. The operational elements of the Amsterdam MLL reflect the characteristics of this specific scheme. We note that a key feature of this scheme was that cars were leased and not privately owned, which is not necessarily the case for all MaaC schemes. The key operational elements included:

- **Vehicle leasing and insurance:** Cars were obtained through leasing contracts which include the costs for maintenance and insurance. The citizens themselves arranged any repairs and maintenance appointment with local garages.
- **Operational support provider:** Members of the MaaC scheme were provided with operational support through the MaaC app's communication layer, which includes a "call centre" feature and was designed as part of the GEMINI project by GoodMoovs. In practice, most issues were resolved by members themselves.
- **Fleet monitoring and fleet management** was carried out entirely by the community members showing the sovereign in holding their data and ownership of the initiative (the local fleet manager).
- **User acquisition, training and onboarding** were carried out by Townmaking and local ambassadors¹. DEEL² trains the ambassadors and provides a network and a platform for knowledge sharing. Through DEEL, fleet managers and local ambassadors are connected to all other managers and ambassadors in the Netherlands. It is noted that, in the Netherlands, the neighborhood cooperatives are organized by DEEL, until they are become self-sustained and independent. At that point, the cooperative also becomes a member and co-owner of the national DEEL cooperative.

¹ Key figures within communities who function as ambassadors to recruit members for the MaaC communities.

² <https://wijzijndeel.nl/>

3. Insights from Amsterdam Mobility Living Lab (MLL) Stakeholder Interviews

In addition to the insights gained from the initial phase of establishing the Amsterdam MLL, we have carried out interviews with the MLL partners to understand how the scheme is progressing and identify any emerging findings. The scheme in Amsterdam has already been taken up by approximately 30 people, who share two vehicles. Preliminary results shows that the user demographic is characterized by a mature age profile, which indicates that schemes are more popular with communities that already have a relative stability in their lives and social circumstances. The participants explained that the Amsterdam MLL confirms findings from other cases, which highlight the value of trust between members of the community and the key role it plays in the concept of MaaC. MaaC schemes are organised between people who already know each other, which means that they often formalise sharing habits that already exist. For example, neighbours may already share rides or friends and relatives may already borrow each other's cars. In addition, these people often share the same social lives, or they may co-organise events and activities, which further enhances trust between them. The fact that schemes are not anonymous often contributes to the better quality of the service and the better condition of the vehicles, compared to conventional rental schemes. However, the fact that MaaC schemes refer to small groups of people – are tailored to their needs – is also exactly what makes them hard to scale up.

The participants also explained how digital technologies can be used to reduce the cost of MaaC schemes, benefitting this way the entire community. Given that users effectively share all the costs of a scheme, including the cost of parking, insurance, equipment, the MaaC application and any liabilities, costs are reduced by either increasing the size of the community or introducing efficiencies. The GEMINI MLL in Amsterdam seeks to reduce the overall cost of running the scheme and to ensure its long-term sustainability through the **communication layer** of the MaaC app. Instead of being “beyond just a chat” between users, this layer makes use of all the different data collected through the hardware of the vehicles to introduce efficiency and reliability in the scheme. For example, it includes automated messages that relate to charging EVs, allowing users to better plan their journeys. In addition, the communication layer is open to non-users, to ensure that the efficiency of operations and user experience is maximised. For example, when cars are due for servicing, the mechanics can book themselves on the app, pick up the car, carry out any servicing and repairs and return it to be used by the community without any of the members having to take this responsibility.

4. Enablers and Challenges for MaaC implementation

This section presents the key enablers and challenges for implementing MaaC driven by the findings from the Amsterdam MLL and concludes with a SWOT analysis.

4.1 MaaC Enablers

The concept of MaaC was first demonstrated in the city of Amsterdam. Amsterdam holds several characteristics that have led to the genesis of the MaaC concept and can be considered as the enablers of the scheme, including: 1. *Progressive Mobility Culture* with high rates of cycling and public transit usage and cultural openness to shared mobility and environmental stewardship; 2. *Strong Urban Planning*: the compact, mixed-use urban area supports active and shared transport; while cycling infrastructure already well-established; 3. *Supportive Local Government*: Amsterdam actively promotes sustainability, innovation, and participatory governance (for example, the city has adopted the Doughnut Economics model (Raworth, 2017); and 4. *Willingness to experiment* with new mobility and commons-based approaches. An advanced data ecosystem, existing smart city initiatives, and open data policies support MaaC integration and innovation.

Furthermore, Amsterdam is supported by the wider community sharing and sustainable mobility context of the Netherlands. Indeed, vehicle cooperatives are well-established in the country, offering pioneering

services to local communities. Cooperatives are also organised in networks, such as DEEL, which is a community of local car sharing cooperatives (<https://www.deel.com/nl/legal/mobility-services/>). At the time of writing, the DEEL included 13 groups and approximately 65 cars, serving more than 500 households. The cooperatives are located across the country, in cities such as the Hague, Amsterdam, Utrecht, and Waterland, and continues to expand. DEEL acts as a knowledge hub and disseminator and aims to support local resilience. They guide citizens through the process of creating their own cooperatives and supporting them in their efforts to expand sustainable mobility in cities, towns and villages. The cooperative also provides the hardware and platform that supports EV MaaC schemes, which can be tailored to the community's needs (The Mobility Factory, no date).

As such, the exercise of “commoning” mobility has been performed in Amsterdam in different ways across case studies and local experiments. Silonsaari (2025) through his research in a remote neighbourhood of Amsterdam, explored providing shared bikes with the goal of supporting ethnic minority, lower-income young people. The results of this study shed light to a key issue: how a bike-friendly city like Amsterdam -still presenting inequalities in the promotion of bike use-, should be co-designed with the local community to achieve optimal efficiency, participation, and equity. Beemer et al. (2024) evaluated Dutch mobility cooperatives as prevailing structures of grassroots innovation. These cooperatives set up community-owned electric vehicle fleets, while questioning established automobility models, with the adoption of collective governance, shared values and sustainability. Even though this initiative presents challenges due to current commodification and policy frameworks, it marked a significant step in enhancing the just nature of mobility transitions. Furthermore, van Lieverloo and Masttrigt (2025) presents a practical roadmap for Common Mobility in Amsterdam, highlighting the importance of strategic partnerships, interactive designs, and community governance to foster broader adoption and systemic change.

4.2 Challenges to MaaC Implementation

In order to establish a MaaC scheme and provide the local communities with the assurance that the scheme serves their needs while safeguarding their rights it is essential to consider and address a range of issues. This section summarises key issues that concern the MaaC “landscape”, which are always considered within their context. The following paragraphs summaries these key issues in eight categories.

- **Regulatory and legal requirements:** MaaC schemes must be compliant with a range of regulatory and legal requirements that apply to different contexts. These include, but are not limited to, legal identity structure and liabilities, data protection rules (such as GDPR), which is essential to ensure the privacy and security of users' information; general consumer protection rules to ensure transparency, fair practices, and the rights of users; competition law; transport regulations such as licensing, insurance and safety standards; environmental standards; VAT; insurance requirements for users and (if applicable) service providers and accessibility requirements.
- **Mapping local stakeholders:** It is essential to understand who are the local stakeholders that are affected by and could shape, facilitate or restrict a MaaC scheme. These include the local government, regulatory bodies, insurance providers, transport providers (including carsharing operators, public transport providers, taxi associations etc.), and, of course, the local residents. Residents can be the individuals that make up the MaaC community but also may include already established bodies, such as residents' associations. Engaging with the local community is important to address concerns, gather feedback, and ensure that carsharing services meet the needs of residents. In addition, collaborating with neighbourhood associations can help address community-specific concerns and foster support for carsharing initiatives.

- **Local geography:** The success of shared services depends on various physical constraints and factors related to the territory, such as urban density, parking availability and permits, charging infrastructure for EVs and public transportation accessibility.
- **Fleet specifications:** It is essential to understand the required and available vehicles specifications, to ensure that they meet local needs but can also be supported by the community. For example, when it comes to cars, they need to be supported by central locking, include the appropriate hardware to connect to the MaaC app, and have adequate range capabilities (if electric).
- **Infrastructure specifications:** these usually include appropriate charging infrastructure but also equipment to support repairs and maintenance.
- **Service scope:** this includes a clear definition of the scheme's objectives and key operational parameters such as coverage, roll-out timeline and KPIs for monitoring. Operational parameters may also include digital reservations of the e-cars, digital key provisioning, a community communication platform, provisioning of the carsharing hardware with integrated key, monitoring on the usage of the vehicles, and monitoring on damages, complaints, misuse, fines, etc.
- **User profiles:** it is important to have a clear understanding of who the scheme refers to. The typical primary users of MaaC schemes are people who are frequently engaged in community actions and possess a valid driving license B and want to share assets – such as a car. The users need to live in the direct surroundings of the location of the shared car (ideally within 500 metres) to make recurring access and usage viable. Users are also often environmentally conscious, cost-conscious, infrequent drivers, have flexible programs, and have an existing preference for shared economy schemes.
- **Digital specifications:** these are centred around the app may include a reservations system, digital key provisioning, administration and payments, helpdesk, and a monitoring framework.

4.3 SWOT analysis

The information acquired from the interviews conducted, along with the input acquired so far from the Amsterdam MLL, supported us in carrying out a **SWOT analysis** (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) for MaaC stakeholders—including policymakers, urban planners, community organizations, and transport providers—has helped better understand the internal and external factors that could affect the success and sustainability of this innovative mobility solution. The SWOT analysis highlights both the transformative potential and the practical challenges of reimagining transportation as a shared, community-centered resource. While its strengths lie in promoting inclusivity, sustainability, and decentralised governance, MaaC must overcome internal limitations such as coordination complexity and funding constraints. MaaC is well-positioned to benefit from global shifts toward environmental responsibility, digital innovation, and collaborative urban planning. However, it also faces external threats from dominant market players, policy and behavioural inertia. To succeed, MaaC initiatives must build on their existing strengths, proactively address weaknesses, and strategically engage with opportunities and risks ensuring mobility systems that are equitable, resilient and genuinely meet each community's needs.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community ownership • User-centric mobility • Equitable Access • Environmental Sustainability • Community empowerment • Local Resilience and control • Behavioural shift from ownership to use • Inclusivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance complexity • Funding and Financial Sustainability • Scalability issues • Technological and Technical challenges • Operational inefficiencies • User Behavior and cultural barriers • Legal and regulatory hurdles
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align with the <u>Doughnut</u> economics • Decarbonizing transport system • Urban sustainability goals • Social Innovation and Inclusion • Digital platforms for sharing • Urban Livability • Community empowerment • Behavioral and cultural shifts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial competition and market capture • Political and institutional resistance • Funding cuts and Economic instability • Digital and Technological risks • Public perception and low adoption • Legal and regulatory barriers • Inequality and exclusion risks

Figure 2: A SWOT Analysis of MaaC

5. A Business Model of MaaC

Based on the insights gathered from the literature review, the SWOT analysis and the insights from the real-life application of MaaC at the Amsterdam MLL, we have developed a MaaC business model utilising the Osterwalder canvas (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010) which is shown on Figure 3. This canvas presents a holistic and novel analysis of MaaC, identifying nine key building blocks (customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure) as well as including social and environmental costs and benefits. The value proposition of MaaC is to create an equitable, accessible and sustainable mobility system, where users have control over how they travel. The ownership and management of the means of mobility is shared among citizens or the local community. MaaC prioritizes cooperative models, participatory decision-making, and shared stewardship of mobility resources. It focuses on citizens within neighbourhoods and their diverse needs, specifically targeting those who may not find current mobility options ideal. Examples include: 1. Residents with Limited Means: MaaC offers a potentially cheaper alternative to car ownership and existing shared mobility options; 2. Environmentally Conscious Residents: MaaC aligns with sustainable practices by promoting car-sharing; 3. Citizens Seeking Convenience and Social Cohesion by encouraging community collaboration, shared responsibilities, and a sense of collective ownership within neighborhoods. Value is generated not just through financial returns, but through reduced congestion, lower emissions, stronger local economies, and improved quality of life.

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Regional authorities Individuals Urban and transport planners Policy makers and regulators Infrastructure and utility providers Parking companies Financial transaction enablers Insurance companies Research organizations Nonprofits and NGOs Private sector partners (vehicles, sensors, charging stations) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of shared vehicle fleets Collective management and usage Service development and provision <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Booking Payment Customer support/service(?) Gathering customer feedback Anchor MaaC with already existing and widely used mobility systems Provide data to authorities Set legal and ethical frameworks for commons-based mobility Ensure interoperability, and privacy <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical and technological resources Human resources (IT professionals) 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collective transport solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote shared access to transport resources Participation: Citizens co-create and co-govern Enhance mobility justice Create a more equitable, accessible and sustainable mobility system Booking and payment Service provided: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexible last mile options Reduced vehicle ownership Improved accessibility Sustainable mobility Cost-beneficial mobility options Social benefits Discount coupons linked to sustainable mobility choices Data provided 	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal assistance Automated services (website, app) Communities Loyalty programs Co-creation (living labs) <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local community groups Website Smartphone apps 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enable diverse mobility needs for various segments: Residents (young, elderly, families, students, low-income, etc.) Cooperatives and Community Organizations
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p><u>Operational costs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amortization of the investment cost Maintenance of the website, app, information system Legal-related costs <p><u>Investment costs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platform and app design and development 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public funding and subsidies Commission from non-mobility service providers 		
<p>Social and Environmental Cost</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Governance challenges Exclusion by participation burden Funding instability Limited coverage and Scaling 		<p>Social and Environmental Benefits</p> <p>Accessibility: Equal access regardless of socioeconomic status or location</p> <p>Sustainability: Environmentally responsible mobility</p> <p>Participation: Citizens co-create and co-govern</p> <p>Transparency: Open access to mobility data and decisions</p> <p>Solidarity: Prioritize collective benefits over individual profit</p>		

Figure 3: The Osterwalder Business Model of MaaC

6. Financing MaaC

MaaC challenges conventional private-sector mobility services and the concept of privately owned mobility by prioritizing collective benefit over individual profit, making it relevant in the transition to more just and sustainable urban transport systems. However, the financial viability of the mobility model depends heavily on the specific needs and characteristics of each community it serves. As such, the cost structure and revenue streams vary depending on the unique dynamics of each location. In terms of revenues, the prices are set by the group of residents themselves, with the aim of covering the costs of the cooperative (i.e. non-profit pricing model). Therefore, the revenues are based on the use of the car by the cooperative members and the chosen pricing scheme, which can be based on simple pricing per km and time of use. We also note that elements of the MaaC ecosystem may have a commercial character, such as the MaaC application, which may be a commercial asset available across different sharing schemes and developed by a for-profit organisation.

In terms of costs, these vary depending on the type of scheme and its characteristics. For example, schemes may use private cars or collectively use cars for sharing; schemes may become members of cooperative associations, which incurs membership fees; or they may use private parking spaces that introduce no additional cost to the community. Typically, when setting up a MaaC scheme, the costs relate to setting up the cooperative (one-off notary costs, certification costs etc.), establishing the schemes digital infrastructure (app fees and any costs associating with tailoring an available product to the community's needs); the vehicles themselves (either fitting private vehicles with sharing hardware or leasing new vehicles); and infrastructure needed to support the scheme (for example parking and charging). The operational costs typically include vehicle maintenance and repairs (including cleaning

and repairing damaged vehicles), vehicle insurance, the costs of running the app, parking charges, banking and accounting services, and, if applicable, membership fees for cooperative associations.

However, it is crucial to note that MaaC schemes are often implemented with the support of government actors, aiming to promote sustainable mobility. Schemes could receive support from local or national governments, or EU funds, which may fund some parts of their operations. As such, financial viability may be a lower priority compared to meeting policy and community needs. For example, in the case of the Amsterdam MLL, the city council supports schemes until they become self-sustaining, facilitating their operation in different ways and helping them find the operational model and partners that suits each community. This is done by connecting them to a variety of alternative partners who provide the elements of the scheme (e.g. hardware and software), giving communities additional time or identifying funding sources when schemes do not meet their initial goals, and helping communities identify vehicles that are already available, thus reducing the cost of the scheme. In addition, the fact that schemes are supported as part of (local) government initiatives may shape their cost structure. For example, certain parking spaces may be provided for free or short trips may be more expensive per km to discourage the use of cars or subsidise the purchase of other vehicles for the scheme, such as cargo bikes. Below we provide an indicative – and context specific – cost structure for the Amsterdam MLL (Table 1). We stress that the figures included are neither definitive nor fully representative of all schemes that could be applied in Amsterdam. These figures are only used to demonstrate an indicative order of magnitude and range categories for a MaaC scheme.

Table 1: MaaC Financing: Development and Operation Costs

Cost Categories for Establishing the MaaC	Proportional Distribution of the Total Cost for Establishing the MaaC
Car delivery and installation of hardware	16%
Back-office costs	33%
Setting up the cooperative (legal advice, chamber of commerce, notary, etc.)	41%
Application for parking space and permit	3%
Construction of the parking space (if applicable)	7%
Running costs of MaaC paid by members	Proportional Distribution of the Running Costs of MaaC
Platform	9%
Lease/ expenses (depending on car)	70%
Charging costs (values indicative for the Netherlands)	8%
General overhead (admin, unforeseen costs etc.)	11%
Membership fee for the National Cooperative	2%

7. Conclusions and Further Research

This paper examined the concept of Mobility as a Commons (MaaC) as an alternative framework to conventional market-driven mobility systems, emphasizing shared ownership and community governance. Drawing on empirical insights from the Amsterdam Mobility Living Lab (MLL), the analysis presented both the theoretical grounding as well as the practical implementation of MaaC. The SWOT analysis identified its key strengths, such as user-centric governance and inclusive access, alongside persistent challenges relating to scalability, funding, and legal frameworks. The proposed business

model, developed through the Osterwalder canvas, reflects the unique characteristics of MaaC, particularly its community-driven nature with emphasis on participatory decision-making, along with its environmental benefits. Unlike commercial mobility models, MaaC relies on collective engagement and seeks to balance financial viability with broader societal objectives. However, despite its promise, MaaC faces several barriers to widespread adoption. A cultural and behavioral shift is critical for transitioning from individual car ownership to shared mobility practices, requiring consistent public engagement, trust-building, and targeted education. The case of Amsterdam MLL illustrates the importance of local context, stakeholder collaboration, and adaptive governance in overcoming these challenges, while also emphasizing that MaaC schemes often build upon pre-existing community ties and shared values.

Financial sustainability remains a central concern in the implementation of MaaC. As demonstrated in the Amsterdam MLL, many schemes operate under cooperative, non-profit principles, with cost structures tailored to local needs and revenue models based on shared usage. While this allows for affordability and local control, it also exposes MaaC to risks related to upfront investment costs, ongoing maintenance, and reliance on public support. However, for MaaC to become truly self-sustaining, further work is needed to identify viable financing strategies that balance collective ownership with long-term economic resilience. A key issue is the scalability and replicability of MaaC across diverse urban and rural set. Finally, to fully realize its potential, MaaC must also be thoughtfully integrated into the broader urban planning framework. Aligning MaaC with the 15-minute city concept (Moreno, 2024) and public space reclamation strategies, such as the creation of car-free zone will reinforce its impact, advancing just, inclusive, and sustainable urban mobility transitions.

Acknowledgements

This research was carried out as part of the GEMINI - Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation Initiatives - project, which has received funding through the HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02 call, and its Grant Agreement number is 101103801. We would like to thank all project partners interviewees for their valuable insights on MaaC.

List of references

- Berger, M., and Dorner, F. (2018). Community-based mobility: a transport option for rural areas? In Proceedings of 7th Transport Research Arena TRA. 7th Transport Research Arena TRA. Vienna.
- Beemer, E., Diercks, G. and Loorbach, D., 2024. From mobility-as-a-commodity to mobility-as-a-commons: Understanding the role of mobility cooperatives in shaping just sustainability transitions. SSRN. [online] Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4798961> [Accessed 25 May 2025].
- Chase, R. (2015). Peers Inc: how people and platforms are inventing the collaborative economy and reinventing capitalism. First edition. New York: Public Affairs.
- Dadashzadeh, N., Woods, L., Ouelhadj, D., Thomopoulos, N., Kamargianni, M., Antoniou, C. (2022). Mobility as a Service Inclusion Index (MaaSINI): Evaluation of inclusivity in MaaS systems and policy recommendations. *Transport Policy*, 127, pp. 191–202. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2022.09.006>.
- Delhomme, P., Gheorghiu, A., and Felonneau, M.L. (2021). What encourages people to carpool? A conceptual framework. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 13, 100498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100498>
- Flores, O. and Rayle, L. (2017) 'How cities use regulation for innovation: the case of Uber, Lyft and Sidecar in San Francisco', *Transportation Research Procedia*, 25, pp. 3756–3768. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.232>.

- Franco, S.F. and Santos, C.D. (2021). The impact of Airbnb on residential property values and rents: Evidence from Portugal. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 88, p. 103667. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2021.103667>.
- Gemini Project (2024). Greening European Mobility through cascading innovation Initiatives. D3.1 Interim Progress Report of Mobility Living Lab Implementation (Public). Available at: <https://www.geminiproject.eu>.
- Graham-Rowe, E., Skippon, S., Gardner, B., Abraham, C. (2011). Can we reduce car use and, if so, how? A review of available evidence. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 45(5), pp. 401–418. ISSN 0965-8564. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2011.02.001>.
- Hensher, D.A., Ho, C.Q., Mulley, C., Nelson, J.D., Smith, G., Wong, Y.Z. (2020). *Understanding Mobility as a Service (MaaS): Past, Present and Future*. Elsevier Inc. ISBN:978-0-12-820044-5.
- Ho, C.Q., and Tirachini, A. (2024). Mobility-as-a-Service and the role of multimodality in the sustainability of urban mobility in developing and developed countries. *Transport Policy*, 145, pp. 161–176. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2023.10.013>.
- Koppelman, F., & Bhat, C. (2024). Understanding Ride-Hailing Sharing and Matching in Chicago Using Travel Time, Cost, and Choice Models (vol 2678, pg 293, 2024). *Transportation Research Record*, 2678(12), 2235-2236.
- Matyas, M., and Kamargianni, M. (2021). Investigating heterogeneity in preferences for Mobility-as-a-Service plans through a latent class choice model. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 23, 143-156.
- Moscholidou, I., Marsden, G. and Pangbourne, K. (2023). Steering Smart Mobility Services: Lessons from Seattle, Greater Manchester and Stockholm. *Sustainability*, 15(5), p. 4566. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054566>.
- Moreno, C. (2024). *The 15-minute City A Solution to Saving Our Time and Our Planet*. ISBN-13: 978-1394228140.
- Müller-Eie, D., and Kosmidis, I. (2023). Sustainable mobility in smart cities: a document study of mobility initiatives of mid-sized Nordic smart cities. *European Transport Research Reviews* 15, 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-023-00610-4>
- Narayanan, S., and Antoniou, C. (2023). Shared mobility services towards Mobility as a Service (MaaS): What, who and when? *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, Volume 168, pp103581, ISSN 0965-8564, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2023.103581>.
- Nikitas, A., Kougiyas, I., Alyavina, E., and Njoya, E. T. (2020). How can autonomous and connected vehicles, electromobility, BRT, Hyperloop, and Mobility-as-a-Service shape transport futures for the context of smart cities? *Urban Science*, 4(4), 36.
- Nikolaeva, A., Adey, P., Cresswell, T., Lee, J.Y., Novoa, A. and Temenos, C. (2019). Commoning mobility: Towards a new politics of mobility transitions. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 44(2), pp. 346–360. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tran.12287>.
- Nikolaeva, A., Adey, P., Cresswell, T., Lee, J.Y., Novoa, A. and Temenos, C., 2018. *A new politics of mobility: Commoning movement, meaning and practice in Amsterdam and Santiago*. CUS Working Paper Series No. 26. University of Amsterdam: Centre for Urban Studies.
- Núñez, C., and Antoniou, C. (2025). The Mobility as a Service Potential Index (MaaSPI): Assessing the conditions for MaaS across countries based on public sources. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*. Volume 60, Pages 101360, Elsevier.
- Osterwalder, A., and Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business Model Generation – A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers and Challengers*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey.

- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511807763>.
- Pagoni, I., Gatto, M., Tsouros, I., Tsirimpa, A., Polydoropoulou, A., Giuseppe, G., Stefanelli, and T. (2021). Mobility-as-a-Service: Insights to policy makers and prospective MaaS operators. *Transportation Letters: the International Journal of Transportation Research*, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2020.1815141>
- Polydoropoulou, A., Pagoni, I. and Tsirimpa, A. (2020). Ready for Mobility as a Service? Insights from stakeholders and end-users. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 21, pp. 295–306. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2018.11.003>.
- Raworth, K. (2017). *Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-Century Economist*. Cornerstone. ISBN 9781847941398.
- Schmaus, A., Creutzig, F., Koch, N., Nachtigall, F., and Molkenhain, N. (2025). An urban shared pooled mobility system cuts distance travelled by over 50%. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, Volume 144, p. 104726, ISSN 1361-9209. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2025.104726>.
- Schor, J.B. (2020). *After the gig: How the sharing economy got hijacked and how to win it back*. University of California Press. ISBN: 9780520385672.
- Shaheen, S., Bansal, A., Chan, N., Cohen, A. (2017). *Mobility and the sharing economy: industry developments and early understanding of impacts*. Chapter 10 In book: *Low Carbon Mobility for Future Cities: Principles and applications* (pp.213-240). DOI:10.1049/PBTR006E_ch10.
- Shaheen, S. (2018). *Shared Mobility: The potential of ridehailing and pooling*, in D. Sperling (ed.) *Three Revolutions*. Washington, DC: Island Press/Center for Resource Economics, pp. 55–76. Available at: https://doi.org/10.5822/978-1-61091-906-7_3.
- Shaheen, S.A. and Cohen, A.P. (2013). Carsharing and personal vehicle services: Worldwide market developments and emerging trends. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 7(1), pp. 5–34. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15568318.2012.660103>.
- Sheller, M. (2020). *Mobility Justice*. In book: *Handbook of Research Methods and Applications for Mobilities*. DOI:10.4337/9781788115469.00007.
- Silonsaari, J. (2025). Assembling velomobile commons for young people in a marginalised Amsterdam neighborhood. *Cities*, 159, p.105763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2025.105763>
- Sopjani, L., Stier, J.J., Hesselgren, M., Ritzén, M. (2020). Shared mobility services versus private car: Implications of changes in everyday life. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 259, p. 120845, ISSN 0959-6526. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120845>.
- Srnicek, N. (2016). *Platform Capitalism*. Polity Press. ISBN 9781509504879.
- van Lieverloo, B. and Masttrigt, S.H. (2025). *Towards a broader user adoption of Mobility as a Commons in Amsterdam: A strategic roadmap for the seamless integration of Mobility as a Commons in Amsterdam*. TU DELFT. Available at: https://repository.tudelft.nl/file/File_b5ce6904-35a5-4dcd-b85e-582e2befb998 (Accessed: 26 May 2025).
- Vega-Gonzalo, M., Gomez, J., Christidis, P., Vassallo, J.M., (2024). The role of shared mobility in reducing perceived private car dependency. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, Volume 126, 2024, pp104023, ISSN 1361-9209, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2023.104023>
- The Mobility Factory (no date). Available at: <https://themobilityfactory.coop/solutions/> (Accessed: 28 May 2025).